

Survey Report

Understanding the Needs, Gaps, and Challenges within the FAIR Community of Trainers

**Maria Vivas-Romero, César Bernabé, Myrthe I. van Heerde, Martijn G.
Kersloot, Paula Ramos-Silva**

Contents

Summary	3
Context	3
Findings	3
Next steps	3
Introduction	4
The survey	4
Results and discussion	4
Survey participants	4
Gaps and needs in the FAIR training landscape	6
Challenges to find and reuse available training in FAIR	9
The way forward: FAIR training resources	12
Conclusions	14
References	15
Annex 1: Resources mentioned by the participants and corresponding DOIs	16

Summary

Context

The aims of the LEARNFAIR project are twofold: 1) to establish a community of FAIR trainers within research organizations, and 2) to establish a set of Open Educational Resources that are approved and adapted by the FAIR data stewardship community. By surveying a cohort of researchers, data stewards, and training developers, this report provides an evidence base for improving FAIR education in the Netherlands.

Findings

While training on the FAIR principles is widely available at Dutch institutions, many survey participants identify existing gaps and needs for developing more advanced and domain-specific, technical training on FAIR topics. Survey participants emphasized that existing materials often lack hands-on, practical application. Furthermore, the community faces systemic barriers to adoption, including limited institutional incentives, lack of time, and insufficient didactical resources for diverse learner profiles. While participants identified a strong demand for formalizing expertise, there is significant concern that traditional, fee-based certification models will introduce inequitable financial barriers. The FAIR training landscape is currently fragmented and suffers from a lack of a structured way of finding and accessing training materials. Lack of metadata and documentation in repositories hinder the discoverability and reuse of materials, resulting in significant duplication of efforts by the community.

Next steps

The next phase of the LEARNFAIR project will be focused on:

1. Conducting interviews with FAIR trainers and educators for a more in-depth understanding of the existing needs, their context, and how they can be addressed.
2. Developing frameworks, such as the FAIR Lesson Plan Handbook, with community of trainers to enhance the findability, accessibility, and reusability of training materials.
3. Develop new training materials within the community that address the existing gaps.

Introduction

The LEARNFAIR project, funded by NWO through the Thematic Digital Competence Centres network (TDCCs) [1], aims at strengthening the Dutch FAIR ecosystem – specifically for the Life Sciences and Health (LSH) domain – by building a dedicated trainers' community and establishing targeted educational resources for educating about the FAIR principles and their implementation. Despite the availability of numerous online resources on FAIR-related topics, a clear understanding of their perceived availability, quality, and effectiveness in addressing training needs has been lacking. The survey described in this report was developed to address this knowledge gap. By identifying the challenges, needs, and gaps faced by trainers, the report provides the evidence base required to improve FAIR training in the Netherlands.

The survey

The survey consisted of two parts. Survey Part I contained 15 optional questions to identify training needs, gaps in resources, and challenges in training on FAIR topics, whereas Survey Part II aimed to collect information about training materials that covered the FAIR principles, using eight optional questions per training resource. Each participant was allowed to complete Survey Part II for as many resources as they wished. The survey opened on September 19th, 2025 and remained available until November 31st, 2025. Distribution outlets included LinkedIn, Teams channels, mailing lists, newsletters, and physical posters and flyers at events. These were targeted at networks, communities, and organizations such as the TDCCs, the Data Stewardship Interest Group (DSIG), local Research Data Management (RDM) professionals and communities, Dutch UMCs, Health-RI, and the Open Science Festival.

Results and discussion

Survey participants

From a total of 72 responses collected in Survey Part I, 64 participants provided formal consent for their data to be processed and analysed. Survey Part II was completed by 15 participants describing 23 resources and offering specific insights into their efforts to create, reuse, and promote FAIR educational content.

Although this sample size is relatively small, it accurately reflects the specialized audience we aimed to reach and the size of a growing community of FAIR trainers. This

community represents a niche group within the Netherlands and worldwide, comprising FAIR training experts currently emerging within universities, university hospitals and other research organizations. The participants of the survey are therefore a representative sample of the active contributors in this developing field, and their detailed input is the primary basis for the findings presented in this report.

The survey was designed and distributed to capture input from a diverse range of professionals within the RDM/FAIR and Open Science ecosystem. Participants included researchers, data stewards, data managers, education specialists, trainers, and IT research software engineers (Fig .1). Unsurprisingly, data stewards represented the largest group at 33%, followed by trainers and researchers at 17%. The remaining roles included research software engineers, education specialists, data managers, and library programme managers. Several respondents indicated that they held two or more roles. The high representation of data stewards is expected, as training and education on FAIR and RDM are formal components of their professional responsibilities in the Netherlands [2]. Many data stewards are responsible for delivering professional RDM/FAIR training to researchers and other staff within Dutch research organizations.

Fig. 1: Distribution of roles.

Responses were gathered mostly from participants based in the Netherlands, Germany and Belgium (Fig .2), and some minor representation from other countries such as Iran, Italy or Cyprus. In the latter cases, we cannot exclude that some participants could

have answered the question considering their country of origin and not the place where they currently work, even though the question explicitly requested the country of employment. Moreover, more than 30 participants chose not to disclose this information.

Fig. 2: Distribution of participants per country where they currently work.

Gaps and needs in the FAIR training landscape

Although the availability of training resources has grown considerably in recent years, important gaps remain regarding several FAIR-related topics. In the Netherlands, most institutions are actively developing training and education on the FAIR principles and Open Science for both students and professionals. However, our survey identifies a number of specialized topics under the four FAIR principles for which training resources are still limited. According to the participants, the gaps in these topics are more pronounced at the expert or more advanced levels (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Gaps in training resources per F-A-I-R categories and expertise levels.

Complementary to the gaps identified above, participants were also asked to indicate their needs regarding training approaches (Fig .4). Practical or hands-on workshops focusing on specific tools and implementation were most frequently selected (24%), followed by advanced technical topics such as ontologies, linked data, or APIs (22%), and discipline-specific training (19%).

Fig. 4: Most needed approaches for training on FAIR.

The gaps in knowledge and training approaches highlighted in the survey corroborate the authors' earlier experiences in recruiting experts for the development of the FAIR Metroline (2026) [3], which provides didactic frameworks for FAIR data and implementation. We observe that expertise in the more technical domains of FAIR is often siloed within specific disciplines or concentrated among research and technical specialists who may not prioritize the pedagogical aspects needed to support a cultural shift and the wider adoption of FAIR practices. Gathering more evidence and context for these observations is a primary objective for the follow-up to the survey, which will involve conducting in-depth interviews to explore the underlying contexts of the current knowledge gaps and trainer's needs.

Beyond content-specific gaps and training approaches, a significant lack of formal certification and recognition remains within the RDM and FAIR landscape. Participants identified this gap primarily in the certification of individual expertise, followed by accreditation mechanisms for repositories, institutions, and training courses (Fig. 5). While there is clear demand for formal recognition, participants also expressed concern that certification fees could create financial barriers and potentially exclude those with limited funding:

“Employers might wear a badge for employing data stewards and supporting fair”

Participant quote 1, 2026

“while I think all of the certification methods listed are good ideas, NONE should be formalised / costly. You should be able to self-certify by making evidence-based content that proves your status as an accredited individual/organisation/project. Cost is a barrier for almost everyone.”

Participant quote 2, 2026

Fig. 5: FAIR certification needs.

Challenges to find and reuse available training in FAIR

In the last part of the Survey Part I, we addressed what are the challenges users identify when trying to find and reuse existing training resources. Finding training is only the first hurdle; participants indicated that locating materials with practical, hands-on examples or exercises was one of the most challenging tasks, with 25 participants highlighting this issue (Fig. 6). This was followed by difficulties in assessing the quality of the available materials (17 responses), and by challenges in discoverability, with 15 participants noting that they did not know where to search for the right resources. In addition, participants also identified other challenges in which existing materials often do not match their specific needs:

Identifying the right didactic concept

Participant Quote 3, 2026

Style: visual or structural misfit to how I want to teach = needs adaptation

Participant Quote 4, 2026

Assess researchers needs and how course material can best relate to this

Participant Quote 5, 2026

Fig. 6: Challenges on finding suitable FAIR training materials

A significant number of participants (21 responses) reported a lack of awareness of what is available (Fig. 7). This is likely due to the rapid proliferation of content combined with the diversified range of repositories and catalogues that host or link to such resources. As a result, the landscape is highly fragmented, making it unclear for trainers where to begin their search or how to approach it in a structured manner. Moreover, insufficient documentation and metadata describing these resources further hinder reuse:

Not enough metadata available to clearly understand

Participant Survey Quote 6, 2026

The training materials themselves are not FAIR.

Participant Survey Quote 7, 2026

In addition to lack of awareness of what training is available, two other issues ranked among the top three: current training is not practical enough (19 responses) and lack of institutional support (16 responses). Finally, respondents pointed to systemic hurdles, indicating that reuse is time and resource intensive:

Training is not modularly prepared for reuse. If I need just a few slides/a method, I usually need to extract it from a pdf (screenshot or rebuild for animations)

Participant Survey Quote 8, 2026

Fig. 7: Challenges on reusing existing FAIR training resources

The way forward: FAIR training resources

In Survey Part II, we asked participants to describe resources they had reused or created themselves. We captured 23 resources, 22 of which had been created by the participant, ranging from workshops, e-learning, slide presentations and other formats (Annex I, Fig. 8). This breadth of materials and formats highlights the community's commitment to creating resources.

Fig. 8: Types of FAIR training resources.

Fig. 9: FAIR topics addressed in the training resources.

With respect to the topics addressed in these resources, the most frequently covered was 'Introduction to the FAIR principles', reported by 19 participants. This was followed by 'Metadata models/schemas' (10 participants), and by 'Use of persistent identifiers' and 'RDM basics', each reported by 9 participants (Fig. 9). More technical aspects of FAIR, such as 'Ontologies' and 'Data models/schemas', were less commonly represented. In addition, certain topics offered in as option in the multiple choice, such as 'SPARQL' were not covered at all. Most courses were targeted at beginners, whereas a

smaller percentage was designed for participants at any training level. None of the resources were directed toward advanced levels of FAIR training (Fig. 10) highlighting a potential gap in training resources for advanced topics.

Fig. 10: Training level of target audience of the training resources.

Conclusions

The LEARNFAIR survey provided a comprehensive view of the knowledge gaps, training needs and challenges in the community of trainers in FAIR. The results evidence a clear need to go beyond introductory coverage of the FAIR principles and develop more practical/hands-on training resources focused on field-specific FAIRification workflows and advanced technical topics. While the community is active in creating new materials, as evidenced by the resources described in Part II of the survey, significant barriers remain that prevent these materials from being more FAIR and reaching a wider audience. In particular, the lack of a structured approach to discovering training resources in repositories and catalogues makes the findability of existing materials a primary barrier for researchers and data professionals alike. Furthermore, the lack of formal recognition for FAIR implementation and training development persists as a major limitation, highlighting the need for more institutional incentives, rewards, and professional validation. The responses also indicate that, although there is clear demand for professional validation of expertise in FAIR, there are concerns about the potential financial barriers that formal certification schemes may create.

To move from a niche community to a sustainable national infrastructure, we must bridge the gap between technical expertise and pedagogical implementation. The next phase of the LEARNFAIR project will dive deeper into the survey findings through qualitative interviews with data professionals that develop pedagogical materials in FAIR and RDM topics. Our goal with these interviews is to move beyond identifying needs and challenges to co-creating solutions, starting with the **FAIR Lesson Plan Handbook** - a community-driven Open Educational Resource [4] to provide systematic guidance to trainers on teaching FAIR. The content of the handbook is currently being developed through interactive Contentathons, which are also part of the LEARNFAIR project.

References

- [1] *Thematic Digital Competence Centres*. (2026). TDCC. <https://tdcc.nl/>
- [2] Jetten, M., Grootveld, M., Mordant, A., Jansen, M., Bloemers, M., Miedema, M., & van Gelder, C. W. (2021). *Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands: Competences, training and education. Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4623713>
- [3] *A step-by-step route to making data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable)*. (2026). FAIR Metroline. <https://fairmetroline.org>
- [4] Kersloot, M. G., Jetten, M., Nylinder, S., Schoots, F., & Cornet, R. (2025). *The FAIR Lesson Plan Handbook: Open Educational Resources for FAIR Training*. *Studies in health technology and informatics*, 327, 1074–1078. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SHTI250548>

Annex I: Resources mentioned by the participants and corresponding DOIs

Training resource	Link
“Handling your research data: everyday pragmatic tips & tricks for PhD students” Research Data Management Awareness	NA
GTN FAIR Learning Materials	https://umcg.capp12.nl/open-courses/courses/1562
Love your Data! Kickstarting Data Organization with a Dedicated Folder Template	https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/fair/
Keep your Project on Track! Plan for Efficient and Reusable Research [Workshop Series]	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17106007
FAIRsharing Educational	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7144126
Data stewardship e-learning	https://fairsharing.org/educational
Draft your Data Management Plan	https://lumc.capp12.nl/open-courses/recourses/169
RDM Tools & Resources with Examples from ELIXIR	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16911851
Love Your Data!	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7101439
Editorial Reference Handbook	https://publishers.fairassist.org/
How to Data — Research Data Management Introduction [Workshop]	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15014195
Love your Data! [Poster]	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7101445
FAIRassist	https://fairassist.org/
Data Publication — Love your Data, Methods, and Materials!	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15013883
Data Management Plans for Beginners [Workshop]	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5575920
Research Data Management Intro Series: Coffee Lectures & Espresso Shots	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7573694
Data Organization: How to Structure Research Data? [Workshop]	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5554825
Publishing Data [Workshop]	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8359792
The FAIR Data Principles - What, why, how?	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096856
Travel Preparations for your Research Journey - Best Practices of Research Data Management and the IPK Support Systems [Workshop Series]	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096586
RDM Reprise & Chorus - Repeat RDM Basics & Find Communities [Workshop]	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8094953
Let's Make a Plan! Using DMPTool to Outline our Research Data Management [Workshop Series]	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8093742